

PECULARITIES OF THE METHOD OF DISCUSSION IN THE FORMATION OF FOREIGN COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Orynbayeva U.

*PhD, associated professor of
Kazakh academy of sport and tourism, Kazakhstan, Almaty*

Ussipbekova N.

*senior teacher of Kazakh academy of sport and tourism,
Kazakhstan, Almaty*

Ospanova A.

*senior teacher of Kazakh academy of sport and tourism,
Kazakhstan, Almaty*

Bolganbayeva B.

*associated professor of
Kazakh academy of sport and tourism, Kazakhstan, Almaty*

Abstract

The article deals with the problem of discussion in activating communicative competence of students in language teaching. The authors expose that teaching a foreign language as a tool for communication continues to be a primary concern in modern methodology. Recently, the focus on the type of learning that stimulates the development of the student's personality and activates their potential has become more widespread. The article substantiates the idea that foreign-language communication is the ability to listen and properly understand the interlocutor, logically and reasonably express an opinion, prove a certain conclusion, find the right solution to a problem, or a way out of a conflict situation. Particular attention is paid to the linguodidactic value of discussion in the formation of foreign language communicative competence. Linguodidactic value of discussion identifies the characteristics of discussion as a communicative method and the conditions for its effective implementation, and presents the basic skills required to participate in a discussion. The authors describe the structural elements of the principles and approaches of discussion in the formation of foreign-language communicative competence. It points out that the discussion used as a method contributes to the activation of students' speech interaction, increases intrinsic motivation to learn a foreign language. It is believed that using discussion as a method contributes to the activation of students' speech interaction and increases intrinsic motivation to learn a foreign language. The authors suggest that the discussion methods hold an intrinsic worth. However, the concept of "discussion method" is clarified in the article and the practical application is shown in the educational process. Finally, the authors give recommendations for the successful organization of discussion. So, the aim is to determine the effectiveness of using discussion in the process of forming students' foreign-language communicative competence. The result of this article showed that discussion method could increase communicative competence of the learners.

Keywords: foreign communicative competence, discussion, formation, foreign language, student, approach, principle.

Introduction

In modern times, higher education institutions strive to not only equip their students with the necessary knowledge and skills for their chosen field, but also to cultivate a lifelong learning mindset in them. This includes the ability to engage in self-development and self-education, adapt to changing circumstances, think critically and creatively, and communicate effectively, particularly in foreign languages (State Compulsory Standard, 2012). To achieve this objective, it is crucial to prioritize language training for students. The national compulsory standard for higher education in the Republic of Kazakhstan highlights the formation of foreign communicative competence as one of the key outcomes of training. This involves equipping students with the skills to communicate effectively with professionals and non-experts, as well as the ability to communicate appropriately in various cultural, social, and specific contexts.

The issue of teaching discussion in a foreign language occupies one of the leading places in the modern foreign language teaching methodology. A significant contribution to the development of the problem of teaching discourse in a foreign language was made by

methodologists who studied various issues, in particular the development of discussion skills as a component of interactive foreign language competence (Chekoldina, 2005), methodological foundations of teaching discussion communication in a foreign language (Azarchenko, 2020), discussion as a method of forming foreign language speaking skills (Salieva, 2016) and foreign language communicative skills (Kopzhasarova, Toktau, 2018).

The research questions were:

- to determine the meaning and significance of educational discourse;
- to define the principles and approaches of discourse;
- to develop tasks for assessing the effectiveness of educational discourse.

However, the substantiation of the peculiarities of organizing the teaching of foreign language discussion with the use of problematic situations has not received proper research.

Different researchers give contrasting approaches in using discussion in teaching foreign languages. Discussion is often regarded as a methodological technique

for developing unprepared speech. It supposes, participation in a discussion will be enough for students to transmit a knowledge about the procedure of discussion (G.A. Rubinstein, V.L. Skalkin, 2012). This approach supposes that discussion skills can develop directly in the process of training.

On the contrary other scientists (Koblova, 1973, Korosteleva, 2020) consider purposeful formation of discussion skills to be a determining factor in teaching foreign language. The operational base is undoubtedly formed by the skills of logical thinking, argumentation, and counter-argumentation, which have to be developed in the teaching process.

Foreign language communicative competence determines the ability and readiness of the student to carry out activities on implementation of communication in a foreign language. Foreign language communicative competence implies the development of abilities and skills in the main types of speech activities, such as speaking, reading, listening, writing, and knowledge of phonetics, grammar, vocabulary, as well as the skill of mastering these above-mentioned competences. E.V. Bibikova shows foreign language communicative competence "as a system formation in a set of motivational, functional and reflexive components (Bibikova, 2006).

In the conditions of the transition to the state standard, the formation of foreign communicative competence of students in the specialty 'Foreign language: two foreign languages' is impossible without knowledge of the English language. Therefore, the relevant method in the formation of foreign communicative competence becomes a discussion. According to A.P. Panfilova, a discussion is "an exchange of opinions on a certain issue in accordance with more or less definite rules, procedure and with the participation of all or individual participants" (Panfilova, 2005). The confrontation of different points of view and positions stimulates speech activity. This forms the ability to calmly listen to the arguments of the opponent, teaches cooperation and critical thinking.

In modern science, there is no unity in explaining the meaning of the term "discourse". However, in many works of domestic and foreign scientists there is a tradition that the word "discourse" is interpreted as a product of speech in a different composition of its cognitive and communicative function.

According to O. F. Rusakova: "discourse" is a speech that, as some researchers note, is figuratively "brought to life" (Rusakova, 2014). Therefore, the term "discourse", unlike the term "text", does not apply to ancient and other texts whose connection with living life is not directly restored.

The concept of "discussion" has been analyzed by foreign researchers from different points of view. One of the foreign scientists Yu.S. Stepanov gives the concept of discussion as "language within a language" (Stepanov, 1995), and at the same time V. Z. Demyankov gives the idea that discussion is a mental text consisting of sentences and fragments (Demyankov, 2015).

T. A. Van Dijk defines discussion as a verbal form of objectification of the content of consciousness, regulated by the prevailing type of rationality in a particular socio-cultural tradition (Van Dijk, 2008).

As for M. McCarthy and R. Carter discourse is a communicative form which is addressed to interlocutor, listener or reader and it has the following characteristics: cohesion, coherence, pattern (McCarthy, Carter, 1994).

According to B. N. Karasik, "communicative discourse applies not only to linguistics; it has an interdisciplinary character. Therefore, it should be understood as a category aimed at regulating the objective perception of society and the peculiarities of interaction within it" [Karasik, 2007].

A. K. Adilova points out the common features and differences of discourse:

- Discourse is broader than text and includes a concept. It is a speech process.

- Discourse is a set of language tools that are requested depending on the authors' intention and style characteristics.

- If discourse is a way of transmitting information, then the text is a multifaceted, multi-layered structure that stores information, accumulates it, and creates new value (Adilova, 2009).

Discourse is a speech activity that takes place between communicants at a certain time and place. That is, the verbal execution of situations in their lives is transferred to the text and preserved in the language as a result of discourse.

The main features of discourse have been analyzed by G. N. Smagulova based on the following characteristics:

- 1) Based on the content around the discourse of a particular topic, in some cases, there may be a change in the subject.

- 2) Social orientation and uncertainty of the volume of the text.

- 3) The content completeness of the discourse is determined by the communicative situation, and if thematic communication is performed, then non-verbal signals are expressed, such as the completion of the text, pauses, and transition to other topics. Therefore, it is impossible to analyze discourse outside of communication relations [Smagulova, 2008].

Communicative discourse expresses the concretization of speech and stable forms of use of speech, communicative behavior, and communication. Communicative discourse characterizes the formal interpretation of communication, the functional interpretation in the formula of the use of language and its units as a communicative and situational nature, and as a characteristic of socio-psychological and socio-cultural situations.

Therefore, discussion method is not only a product of speech activity, but also the process of its construction. The discourse is determined by extralinguistic factors, such as the communicative context and the conditions of communication. At the same time, the strategy of verbal communication, the verbal and non-verbal behavior of communicants, as well as the type, form, and content of the created or perceived text, are determined by this cultural context and the communicative goals of communicative individuals.

Methods and materials

The purpose of this study was to study the level of formation communicative competence under the means

of discussion. In our study, the authors made an attempt to experimentally test the formation of communicative competence under the means of discussion. Experimental work was carried out to determine the effectiveness of using the discussion method in foreign language classes.

The discussion, unlike other methods, allows you to use the discussion as a mental tool that gives each participant the opportunity to understand their inner world and the world of others, to see themselves from the outside and through the eyes of other people, to see the possibilities and directions of their own change.

During the discussion, co-creation relations are created between the participants, which provides a more intensive process of self-development and self-realization, contributes to the rethinking of one's own experience. The discussion was realized through assignments at seminars in the discipline "Methodology of foreign language education".

The purpose of the article was to investigate the extent to which speech skills of students can be developed through the use of educational discussion. As a control group was taken 3rd year students of the specialty 6B01705 "Foreign language: two foreign languages" Zhetysu university named after Iliyas Zhansugurov (Taldykorgan, Kazakhstan).

The aim of the article is to determine the peculiarities of the organization of teaching foreign-language discussion in higher education.

Objectives of the research:

- based on the analysis of scientific literature to determine the peculiarities of foreign-language discussion;
- to substantiate the stages of teaching discussion using problem situations in the foreign language classes at the university.

The introductory part of the article describes the essence and content of the educational discussion.

Discussion method has a collaborative, social character, representing inter-subjective and playful activity and fulfilling learning, developing, educational, and stimulating function. In order to organize discussion communication, students must have a high degree of maturity and independence in acquiring knowledge

and formulating problems, in selecting and clearly presenting their own arguments.

Discussions can be held in small groups and it is important to determine what teachers call small groups (4-6 students). Teamwork not only increases student engagement, but also promotes the development of social skills, better communication and more autonomy (Karaev, 1997).

The discussant must be able to express his/her opinion accurately, to build a logical argumentation, to refute an opponent or convince him/her of the correctness of his/her point of view. At the same time, the discussant should remember the need to find a joint solution, which encourages him/her to listen attentively to his/her interlocutors and to correlate their statements with his/her own arguments. All these skills and abilities, formed in the process of educational discussion, are the key to successful communication.

The organization of the discussion predetermines and reinforces the verbal confrontation. In turn, this helps to establish interaction between the participants and regulate the entire discussion process. Discussion is critical to the productive exploration of a problem. In order to fruitfully investigate an instructional discussion problem, it is necessary to know and master the principles that help students interact with each other and determine the entire discussion process that follows.

The process of forming students' foreign-language communicative competence under the means of educational discussion is organized in accordance with certain principles. They reflect the internal essential sides of students' activity; determine the effectiveness of learning in various forms with its content. The principles also, express the normative foundations of learning.

When determining the principles of the discussion, the authors took as a basis the principles of the author T.E. Damer. The researcher thinks that these principles will help the productive work of the discussion in teaching a foreign language. In the formation of foreign language communicative competences in the learning process the following principles: principle of the search for truth, principle of clarity and principle of acceptability (Damer, 2009).

Figure 1. Principles of discussion in formation foreign communicative competence (Complied T.E. Damer).

The principle of seeking the truth - the concept of "truth" in a particular case is difficult to define; the best solution is the position that is most acceptable to all par-

ties. Therefore, it is necessary to be prepared for alternatives that diverge from your own, to gather information about them in advance if possible, and to allow

other participants to present arguments or object to any position related to any controversial issue.

The principle of clarity – implies asserting and supporting thoughts with arguments, and our speech should be as simple and clear as possible. It is necessary to show clearly where our position is congruent with that of the opponent, and where it is inconsistent.

The principle of acceptability is to share universal values and knowledge, so that in most cases, it is possible to find a commonly known point of view on an issue that is clear to everyone, and to start from it in our further reasoning.

The success of setting goals for the formation of foreign communicative competence in discourse depends on how competent and linguodidactic approach is used. The competence approach is optimally combined with active and interactive methods of learning, which are most often characterized by a combination of non-standard forms, means, and methods aimed at organizing the educational space. A person's personality develops in the process and as a result of solving situations that are vital to them. To develop professional thinking and organizational skills, it is necessary to systematically put students in conditions that allow them to exercise one or another type of activity.

The aim of the communicative approach in teaching a foreign language is to develop foreign communication skills and abilities in the target language (Lebedev, 2004). Discussion stimulates the speech activity of students and enables one to adopt a differentiated approach towards the formation and development of communicative abilities and personal qualities. This, in turn, allows students to adapt in the social environment and effectively solve the problems of personal and professionally significant communication.

Effective education of students today requires methodologists to work in a new direction. That is why many scientists and methodologists-teachers, as a result of their research and experience, came to the conclusion that one of the ways to revive the learning process is to use training and tasks in the classroom with a sample of various new technologies [Westwood, 2008].

The task "Working in group".

The aim of the task: to develop the ability to place and analyze the situation from the point of view of another person. Description of the task. The teachers are asked to divide into two equal groups: the first group is "trainees" and the second is "teachers". Each group is offered to discuss the task and create rules in the group. 3-5 minutes are given to work in groups. After the discussion, each group should write its own rules with markers and choose the person who will represent the outcome of the group's work.

Groups take turns to present the results of their work, and then together select the same rules, discuss them and create general rules based on positive language, without writing them out on a blank sheet, and each signs under these rules, the rules are placed on the board.

At the end of the work, an exhibition of drawings is made and samples are posted. Group members discuss the results.

How did you feel about being the "intern" and the "teacher"?

Would you like your work to be appreciated, why?

The next topic: "Learning environment is a source of spiritual wealth". Taking part in the discussion on this topic, students were required to prove their point of view on this issue and be able to defend it. At the beginning of the lesson, students were divided into groups of supporters and opponents.

The purpose of the discussion method is as follows: firstly, the students have the ability to speak freely, correctly; secondly, it develops the system of thinking, expands the worldview; affects the formation of personal views as a person; thirdly, forms virtues, moral qualities. The task of the group of supporters participating in the discussion lesson: they introduce their group, defend their individual point of view on each argument, answer counter questions and ask questions. Opponent group also introduce themselves, object to the arguments of their opponents, and ask questions.

Both groups should proof:

1. What is the educational environment and what it is like?

2. Implementation of the modern educational environment and necessary initiatives / steps to overcome them.

3. The person who stops working in group also stops thinking.

4. The learning environment encourages students to find the necessary information on their own.

The final part of the discussion is the conclusion of it. The results of the thought section are summed up by the teacher.

Based on the above, the authors can emphasize that the principles and approaches of discussion application in the formation of foreign language communicative competence give students ample opportunities for the development of speech skills and the activation of foreign language communication. It helps to stimulate interest in the subject and serves the best assimilation of lexico-grammatical material.

The authors consider it appropriate to use discussion at all levels of foreign language teaching because it not only adds variety but also makes the lesson bright and dynamic.

The discussion method provides students with the chance to analyze received information and reach a well-reasoned decision together on the given topic. This method also aids in removing communication barriers, improving their vocabulary, and effectively planning their statements.

Furthermore, it facilitates active and thorough learning and encourages interaction between students. Through discussions, students can compare and assess their viewpoint, which in turn boosts their educational and developmental skills. Ultimately, discussion method stimulates students' speech activity.

Results and discussion

To evaluate the progress of discourse learning, it's essential to establish the standards and signs that enable us to track their progress over time. Considering the diverse interpretations of these terms, it's important to clarify their definitions. A criterion refers to a qualitative feature of a phenomenon or concept that is based on common characteristics, and it serves as the foundation for any classification. It represents a generalized

attribute of development within similar systems, allowing for differentiation between them [24, p. 98]. On the other hand, an indicator describes a quantitative or qualitative feature of the studied object that depicts the phenomenon concerning criterion evaluation [Zeer, 2007].

Based on the analysis, the authors have identified the criteria for the effectiveness of learning discussions in the process of participation in the discussion. The indicators and criteria for the effectiveness of learning discussions include the following: actively participating in the discussion and formulating one's own viewpoint, attentively considering and acknowledging the perspectives of others, presenting and advocating for one's own stance, and public speaking.

Summarizing the studied materials, the authors have distinguished three universal criteria for the effectiveness of educational discussion: dialogicality, creativity, and reflexivity. Communicativeness is an indicator of the criterion of dialogicality, referring to the capacity to initiate and sustain connections grounded in the principles of dialogical communication. Indicators of the creativity criteria are the number of ideas arising per unit of time, originality (the ability to produce unusual ideas that differ from the conventional), and flexibility. An indicator of the reflexivity criterion is the ability to analyze and self-analyze, evaluate and self-assess, plan and forecast activities and their results.

Based on the principles, approaches, and criteria the authors have developed, a number of tasks were

given to the students. The following topics were developed with the students:

1) It is suggested that higher education in higher educational institutions should be fully paid for.

2) The introduction of the Bologna system in Kazakhstan disrupts the educational process.

When discussing the first topic, students made the following conclusion: The question of whether higher education should be for a fee is not just about money. It is a question of the value of four years of a young person's life for their future. The question of whether it is worth attending university and whether one should have to pay for it will continue to be debated as long as the value of obtaining a diploma is not apparent and its link to future success is not always established. The question remains open and requires further discussion. It is not necessary to go to university right out of high school, as 65% of freshmen have maintained contact based on the values of dialogic communication and what they want out of life.

However, I still think that higher education is necessary. The main thing is to find a reputable university and consume education properly, not just attend classes with an iPhone. 16% of respondents were able to produce unusual ideas that the importance of a university degree is greatly exaggerated. 19% believe that planning and forecasting activities are necessary, and it is essential to learn another profession independently.

Figure-2. Results of the discussed topic in formation foreign communicative competence (compiled by the authors)

According to the results of the discussion by the students of this question, the authors determined that 52% of students showed flexibility that Kazakhstan's accession to the Bologna process will ensure the recognition of Kazakhstani educational programs, curricula, academic mobility of students and teachers, convertibility of domestic diplomas in the European region, the right of graduates for employment in any country. 23% unification of education and control (above all, the test

system) creates an opportunity to rote the necessary material, does not dispose to critical thinking and the ability to ask questions instead of choosing answers from a list offered. 25% of students assessed and analyzed that a bachelor's degree is often perceived as incomplete or incomplete higher education, the wage rate with such a diploma is significantly lower even and bachelors are treated less prejudicially.

Figure-3. Results of the discussed topic in formation foreign communicative competence.
(Complied by the author)

Based on the results of the study, the authors have observed positive trends in all criteria, and improvements in indicators such as argumentativeness, communicativeness, flexibility, originality, and the ability to analyze and self-analyze. This leads us to conclude that discussions in English classes are an effective teaching method that helps to develop foreign language communicative competence in students. Moreover, it generates an undeniable interest among students, both in terms of form and content.

Comparison of the results obtained with the results of other studies. When working on the task, students interact with each other to work out different sentences and expressions, examples of their grammatical and lexical units of language, pronunciation of words. Students focus on solving various problems through the norms of linguistic interaction with the participants in the discussion and, after completing the discussion, have the opportunity to analyze the entire discussion as well as the individual participants and their statements. Consequently, discussion skills develop skills for interaction in professional and learning environments and contribute to the development of communicative competence. The main value of discussion communication is learning to interact.

The analysis of the collected materials allowed us to come to the conclusion that the application of the principles of the search for truth, clarity and acceptability in the process of forming the communicative competence of students using the discussion method is effective. The authors came to this conclusion on the basis of a deep and comprehensive analysis of the linguodidactic requirements for principles, taking into account the methodological possibilities of teaching disciplines. The practical significance lies in the fact that the task developed by us was effectively used in the process of teaching the discipline "Methods of foreign language education".

Therefore, the effectiveness of training discussions was proven in the formation of foreign language communicative competence in English classes, and it is

necessary to include such classes in the educational process.

Conclusion

Based on the above, the authors have concluded that, in general, the method of discussion can be utilized to develop the speaking skills of students in a language institute. To achieve this goal, teachers should carefully prepare the material, taking into account the features of this method, the curriculum, the purpose of the lesson, and the topic. Additionally, it would be advisable to build learning cycles in stages according to the level of students' language proficiency in the basic skills of discussion, such as reasoning and argumentation. The use of the "Discussions" method in English classes offers an opportunity to:

- Form both linguistic and speech skills of students
- Train thinking and understanding specialists who are ready for open and constructive dialogue with colleagues from different countries and cultures
- Teach students to create models of scientific research and decision-making that they can apply not only in their professional activities but also in everyday life, in the process of communicating with representatives of other cultures.

In conclusion, the authors note the important role of discussion in the development of students' personalities. With the help of a foreign language, students gain necessary perspective for self-realization and disclosing their creative potential. This method fosters not only students' speech culture but also creates necessary conditions for finding independent solutions to discussed problems, which is a driving force of learning. Using the method of discussion in teaching a foreign language, in addition to improving students' foreign language communication skills, develops their critical thinking and creates conditions for the use of personal life experiences and previous knowledge for assimilation of new ones.

Based on the above, the authors can emphasize that the use of discussion in the study of a foreign language gives students ample opportunities to develop

speech skills, enhance foreign language communication, stimulate interest in the subject, and better absorb lexical and grammatical material. It is appropriate to use discussion at all levels of foreign language teaching because it introduces variety and makes the lesson bright and dynamic.

To summarize, the authors would like to highlight the advantages of using discussion as a method for developing foreign language communicative competence in comparison to using native language discussion in terms of communicative competence development. Learning a foreign language itself disciplines, organizes, promotes logical thinking, and increases self-control. Discussion in any language is a universal means of teaching interpersonal communication. Thus, the discussion method not only fosters a culture of speech, but also encourages students to find independent solutions to the problems discussed which, in turn, a driving force for cognitive activity is. The application of this method in teaching a foreign language forms a culture of creative thinking in students, creates conditions for using personal life experience and previously acquired knowledge to assimilate new information.

References

1. State Compulsory Standard of Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Higher Education, Bachelor's Degree. Basic provisions, approved by the Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated August 23, 2012, № 1080.
2. Chekoldina, A.V., 2005 The development of discussion skills as a component of interactive competence in students of non-linguistic universities. Author's abstract of the dissertation ... candidate of pedagogical sciences. Pyatigorsk.
3. Azarchenko, G. Y. 2020. Methodological bases of teaching discussion communication in a foreign language. Topical issues of the methodology of teaching foreign languages: collection of scientific articles. Cheboksary, pp.3-7.
4. Salieva, Z.I., 2016 Discussion as one of the methods of forming speaking skills in English lessons. Pedagogy of higher school, № 3, pp.63-65.
5. Kopzhasarova, U.I., Toktau, M.K., 2018 The development of foreign-language communicative skills of high school students through the use of the method of discussion. Scientific review. Pedagogical sciences. 2018; № 3: pp.19-23.
6. Skalkin, V. L., Rubinshtein, G. A., 2012 Educational discussion as a means of developing unprepared speech. Foreign languages at school, No. 8, p.18-25.
7. Koblova, J.P., 1973 Methodology for teaching discussion in the third year of a language university (on the material of the German language): Dis. cand. ped. sciences. M., p. 233.
8. Korosteleva, S. G., 2020 The development of pedagogical thinking in the professional training of future teachers. Educational standards and pedagogical practice. Science and School / Science and School No. 4. 2020, pp. 73-81.
9. Bibikova, E.V., 2006, Formation of the bases of foreign-language communicative competence at the future ecologists: Avtoref. diss. cand. ped. nauk. Maykop.
10. Panfilova, A. P., 2005, Business communication in professional activity: textbook / A. P. Panfilova; St. Petersburg Institute of Foreign Economic Relations, Economics and Law, Society "Knowledge" of St. Petersburg and the Leningrad region. - 3rd edition. - Saint-Petersburg: Zanyes, p. 495.
11. Rusakova, O.F., 2014, Discourse, Political Discourse, Political Discursology // Diversity of Political Discourse, Yekaterinburg, p.23
12. Stepanov, Y.S., 1995, Alternative world, discourse, fact and the principle of causality / Y.S. Stepanov // Language and science of the 20th century. - Moscow: Institute of Linguistics of RAI, p. 420.
13. Demyankov, V.Z., 2015, Language of science as an element of cultures // The role of humanities in modern society: State and prospects. Collection of articles. - Moscow: Russian State University for the Humanities, pp. 149-161.
14. Van Dijk, T. A., 2008 Discourse and Context: A Socio-Cognitive Approach. Cambridge. - New York: Cambridge University Press, p.125.
15. Mccarthy, M.J., Carter, R.A., 1994, Language as Discourse: Perspectives for Language Teaching, Harlow: Longman, p. 230.
16. Karasik, B.N., 2007 The Language Circle: Personality, Concepts, Discourse. - Moscow: Gnosis.
17. Adilova, A. 2009, An intertextual representation, semantics, structure in modern Kazakh works of Art Phil.science. doct. Thesis, Almaty, p.235.
18. Smagulova G. N., 2008, Discourse of eloquence. - Almaty, p. 17-18.
19. Karaev, M., 1997, Problems of lesson methodology. Training manual. Book 1. - Almaty: Rauan, p.97.
20. Damer, T.E., 2009 Attacking Faulty Reasoning: A Practical Guide to Fallacy-Free Arguments. - Belmont.
21. Lebedev, O.E., 2004, Competence approach in education//School technologies. - 2004. – № 5.